

LINGUISTIC-DIDACTIC ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL-PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH TEXTBOOKS OF GRADE 5-7.

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Abstract ; In the article phraseological units about information , their come exit history and lexical-phraseological units on searched for scientists and their views about sources light up given

Key words ; phraseology , lexicological units , phrases , phraseology units , proverbs , expressions .

Phraseology (Greek phrasis is " expression " , logos is " doctrine " in language steady compounds learner of linguistics department . Phraseologisms in general in the language , it is known one the writer in the language , it is known one artistic work in the language and etc steady compounds set also called Phraseologism word with one different it's not and to him complete equivalent not Phraseological in the phrase expressed semantic meaning one word with not but two or from him more than word compound with expressed for it is more complicated type lexicon is unity . Phraseologism from the word to the structure according to difference does : word of morphemes consists of is , har how phraseological unity , first of all , is known one language grammar laws (separately phrasal verb to be made and whole word to be made) on the basis of united word is a combination . Phraseological of units structural parts mutually in connection free will not be their another words with compatibility scope closed Phraseologisms lexicon stability with separate stands , mainly constant content

keeps.

Independent as a linguistic discipline phraseology relatively recently appear was Subject and duties , him learning scope and methods yet sure unmarked , they complete cover not received Phraseological of units free word compounds relatively main signs , phraseology of units classification and their parts of speech with relationship and others about questions to others than less work developed. This of units in the language composition . Some researchers (LPSmit , VPZhukov , VN Telia , NM Shansky and others) to phraseology his stable compounds , others (NN Amosova , AM Babkin , AI Smirnitsky and others) - only known groups own into takes that telling have passed So , some linguist scientists (including academic _ VVVinogradov) proverb , matal and joint the words phraseological units to the series including , they phraseological from units semantics and syntactic to the structure according to that is different they count . VV Vinogradov : Proverb and words to sentence structure have of words semantic equivalent it's not that emphasized .

It is known that it is phraseological units portable in a sense applicable of words free from the compound harvest will be Phraseological unity of components nominative meanings how transfer , in them portable of meaning How strong that looking VVVinogradov them - phraseological combinations , phraseological units and phraseological associations that three type divides;

1. Phraseological units - words so stable compounds being , in them common figuratively meaning there is when , structural of parts semantic division signs sure preserved remains : beans pour out throwing - the secret to open frying for another to the fish have to be more important to work have to be to be narrow in the shoulders - a joke do not understand ; the devil from himself according to black to color paint - exaggerate show. Phraseological units his own imagery , metaphor in terms of phraseological to compounds one until is closer . But figuratively content only diachronic way openable phraseological from

compounds different as , phraseological in units figuratively , transfer modern language point of view in terms of done is increased . Academician VV Vinogradov imagery only phraseological to units special feature that knows.

2. Phraseological associations or idioms absolutely indivisible , inseparable steady compounds being their common meaning them organize doer of words meaning depends won't be : the bucket to kick is colloquial in the language this to bend , to die ; = his legs to stretch, be at smb.'s beck and call - har always to the service ready be _ = assignments perform _ a cat and the dogs rain - bucket such as pour (rain about Phraseological compounds their structural parts portable meanings based on appear was , but later this portable meanings modern language point of view in terms of you don't understand being the rest Phraseological of compounds imagery only historical in terms of opens Or , for example , all thumbs phrase historically of the fingers all thumbs up from the expression come came out

3. Phraseological compounds steady turns they are _ in the composition free and phraseological in terms of connected the words own into takes a narrow escape - a miracle get rid of , frown frown - frown put put , Adam Apple - Adam Apple , Sisyphus work is yours to work , to rack the brain (to think see , remember), pay to someone attention _ - to someone attention to give and etc. Overall inseparable to the meaning have has been phraseological compounds and phraseological from units different respectively phraseological compounds semantic break up feature with separate stands In this respect they are free to phrases near.

So , phraseological in compounds directly _ and portable meanings between dependence lost , they for figuratively meaning main being the rest That's why for phraseological compounds another to languages translation to do difficult

_ Phraseology complicated event being him _ learning to himself special research method , as well as another sciences lexicology , grammar , stylistics , phonetics , language history , history , philosophy , logic and country studies from the data to use Demand.

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